

CURRENT SCENARIO OF DIGITAL MARKETING- A SNAP SHOT OF DIGITAL INDIA

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Abstract – Digital Marketing is extending in India with quick speed. A few Indian organizations are involving digital marketing for serious lead. Most part as definitive job is played by web in advanced promoting. Far and wide fuse of the web for both business and confidential use has created many new channels for publicizing and advertising exercises. This article fundamentally centers on the development of advanced promoting in the current situation. The review attempted plans to find the peculiarity connected with the tendency in computerized promoting. Consequences of this study uncover that all substances concur in regards to required web mindfulness for the development in computerized advertising in this review.

Keywords – Digital Marketing; Digital Media; Marketing; Promotions; Digital advertising

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing is marketing of goods or services, which involves electronic devices. Digital advertising is widely referred to as ‘online advertising’, ‘internet advertising’ or ‘web advertising’. Digital advertising means the advertising of goods or services by means of digital technologies. The form of marketing which revolves around internet based promotional messages to target the consumers. Digital technology includes internet, mobile phone or any other digital media. In 1981 the first PC was launched by IBM and for the first time Channel Net Soft Advertising Group an ad firm which attempted to involve many ad campaigns in soft form with the support of advertising digitalization launched the digital marketing concept which give raise to promotional trials such as Reader Reply Cards predicted in Magazines and in return acquiring the floppy disk which comprises of multimedia content (Kamal, 2016). The below figure shows the evolution and history of digital marketing:

Figure 1: Evolution and History of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a bunch of incredible assets and techniques utilized for advancing items and administrations through the web. It incorporates extensive variety of promoting components than in conventional business advertising because of the additional channels and showcasing systems accessible on the web. Computerized showcasing moves at the speed on light to keep up areas of strength for a with the judgment to think basically, act freely and be steadily innovative. Web is a component to make the life simple and quicker. In the current situation we can see that computerized showcasing assumes a significant part supplanting the customary promoting.

II DIGITAL MARKETING CHANNELS

1. SEO (Search Engine Optimization)

Search engine optimization (SEO) is the procedure of moving the visibility of a website or a web page in a search engine's "natural" or un-paid ("organic") search results. SEO may mark different kinds of search,

including image search, local search, video search, academic search, news search and industry-specific vertical search engines.

As an Internet marketing strategy, SEO considers how search engines work, what people search for, the actual search terms or keywords typed into search engines and which search engines are preferred by their targeted audience. Optimizing a website may involve editing its content, HTML and related coding to both increase its relevance to specific keywords and to eliminate barriers to the indexing activities of search engines. Endorsing a site to increase the number of back links, or inbound links, social bookmarking, directory submission is another SEO tactic.

2. SEM (Search Engine Marketing)

Search engine marketing (SEM) is a form of Internet marketing that includes the advertising of websites by increasing their visibility in search engine results pages (SERPs) through optimization. SEM may use search engine optimization (SEO), which adjusts or rewrites website content to achieve a higher ranking in search engine results pages, or use pay per click listings.

3. SMM (Social Media Marketing)

Social media marketing is the process of gaining website traffic or attention through social media sites. Social media marketing programs typically put efforts to create content that attracts attention and inspires readers to share it across their social networks. The resulting electronic word of mouth (eWoM) refers to any statement consumers share via the Internet (e.g., web sites, social networks, instant messages, news feeds) about an event, product, service, brand or company. When the fundamental message spreads from user to user and probably vibrates because it appears to come from a trusted, third-party source, as opposed to the brand or company itself, this form of marketing results in earned media rather than paid media.

ONLINE MARKETING IN INDIA

India has a web client's base of about 450 million as of July 2018, 40% of the populace. The business agreement is that development is at an expansion point. In India, money down is the most favored installment technique, collecting 75% of the e-retail exercises. In country with a quick development economy, it is normal to have an extremely high critical development in computerized promoting vocation. The development in web based promoting patterns is having an exceptionally significant effect on showcasing and commercial. The utilization of specialized apparatuses has extraordinarily changed in the year past. A few variables have been found to add to the development of computerized showcasing in India. Before now, web utilization was just implied for the rich. There is currently an extraordinary change in the way of life of the working class. The very larger part currently approach the web in India. Web and 3G entrance reformed the showcasing situation for the two purchasers and the advertisers. The accompanying overview from individuals shows the size of Digital Marketing industry in India:

- 34% of the companies already had an integrated digital marketing strategy in 2018
- 72% marketers believe that traditional model of marketing is no longer sufficient and this will make the company revenue to be increased by 30% by the end of 2019

In 2019, 80% organizations will build their advanced promoting spending plan which might outperform the IT spending plan. Just the uneducated people couldn't get to the possibilities of the advanced promoting due to the openness to processing gadgets and PC instruction. A significant number individuals

in this classification actually have little to no faith in the technique for a web-based installment and they need preparing in English Language and other unknown dialects to showcase online in worldwide business sectors.

III The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To study the role of digital marketing in Indian scenario.
2. To identify various reasons and schemes that affecting the growth of digital marketing.
3. To study the opinions of three entities viz. consumer, company and 3rd party agency with regard to the growth of digital marketing.

IV REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sharad Madhukar Dashaputre (2011), in his thesis “A study of the growth of internet marketing in Indian scenario” came to a conclusion that an increase in the use of internet and mobile has resulted for the increase in the growth of internet marketing. Based on their study all the respondents agree that internet is mandatory for the growth of online marketing and hence people should be given awareness of internet. Most of them strongly agree that traditional marketing will be replaced by online marketing in the near future.

Susanne Schwarzl and Monika Grabowska (2015), in their study on the topic “Online marketing strategies: the future is here” said that studying the customers' behavior is important in all the type of marketing activities. Whether it is online or offline customers behave in the same way. An apt strategy should be used for bringing the attention of customers.

No company activities move without internet. So it is important to have at least one online department for the company's web presence. The main goal of company should be to create a clear defined brand which represents the companies values and catch potential buyers and loyal consumers attention offline as well as online.

Niharika Satinder (2015), in their journal “A study on internet marketing in India: Challenges and Opportunities” says that online marketing develops a greater opportunity to get information relating to customers as compared to traditional methods of marketing. In the next few years online marketing will strengthen more and makes the shopping habits pf the people more efficient and world class. Because of the use of credit cards the online shopping became easier.

Vladislav Yurovsky, in his study “Pros and Cons of Internet marketing” came to a conclusion that there are advantages as well as disadvantages for internet marketing. Some of the advantages are empowering effect, elimination of geographic barriers, target reaching, immediate results, cost effective, reaching wider or international auditory, measurable result, can be personalized, relationship build, 24 hours/ 7 days availability. Internet marketing also have some disadvantages such as copying, too much add cutter, unserious perception, unconformity to the product, too much competition, and damage by negative feedback, technological dependence, and were not embraced by all people and lack of trust.

D.K Gangeshwar (2013) in his journal, “E-commerce or internet marketing: a business review from Indian Context”, remarked that the present developed in online marketing would be a valuable addition to researcher and academicians and useful theory for practitioners, advertisers and entrepreneurs. In the

next three to five years India will have 30 to 70 million internet users which will equal many of the developing countries. E-commerce is set to play a very important role in the 21st century, the new opportunities that will be thrown open, will be accessible to both large corporations and small companies.

Dr.Amit Singh Rathore, Mr.Mohit Pant, Mr. Chetan Sharma (2017), in their article “Emerging trends in Digital marketing in India” says that the consumers are looking and searching more on internet to find the best products and services from the sellers around India. By different techniques of digital marketing such as search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, e-commerce marketing, campaign marketing, social marketing etc. the shopping speed of the customers have been increased vastly. The usage of social media has created new opportunities for digital marketers to attract the customers through digital platform.

Among all modern marketing techniques, digital marketing and social media are becoming the most significant. Digital marketing is now often regarded as the most important marketing component (Mandal et al., 2017).

Digitalization now affects both consumer and industrial marketing. Industrial marketing researchers and practitioners must comprehend this. Recognize it by practicing it is to know digital marketing's current capabilities (Herhausen et al., 2020).

V. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study aims at studying client servicing and business development process. It is a continuous process followed by six steps which are important that their level.

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This study helps me to get the reality check of a market where actual comparison between the classroom knowledge and the real situation can be done. By just learning theory and facing actual situations it concepts and practices might vary. The study helps to understand the different concepts of digital marketing, but while implementing it might differ from situation to situation.

This study helps to understand and know how to deal with different kinds of customers or a clients and how to make an impressive online campaigns.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive study is a fact finding investigation with adequate interpretation. The descriptive study aims at identifying the various characteristics of a problem under study. It reveals potential relationships between variables and also setting the stage for further investigation later. The results of such research are not usually useful for decision making by them, but they can provide significant insight into a given situation. Although the results of qualitative research can give some indication as to the ‘why’, ‘how’ and ‘when’ something occurs, it cannot tell us ‘how often’ or ‘how many’.

As the research conducted was observatory there was no questionnaire and hence no sample size or data interpretation was to be done.

Secondary Data:-

Secondary data is collected from already existing sources in various organization brochures & records. Secondary data for the study were collected from the magazines, websites & other previous studies.

To meet the objectives, the study used qualitative research. The descriptive study was done through review of existing literature that helped in validation and extraction of the important variables and factors. Data was collected from secondary sources. Secondary sources were magazines, websites, books, office executives, and company data.

Digital Marketing Industry in India

Digital Marketing industry in India is spread to almost all the business sectors. Some of the applications of E- Marketing are shopping and order tracking, online banking, payment systems and content management.

The power of digital marketing allows geophysical barriers to disappear making all consumers and businesses on earth potential customers and suppliers. It is known for its ability to allow business to communicate and form a transaction anywhere and anytime.

Digital marketing industry in India is a booming career today. In a country with a rapid growth economy, it is expected to have a very high significant growth in Digital marketing career. The growth in the digital marketing trends is making a very substantial impact on marketing and advertisement. The big picture of Digital Marketing industry in India cannot be complete if short preview of the past digital marketing statistics is not made.

The portion of promotion spends on cell phones across India were supposed to arrive at 77% of the all out computerized media use by 2022. This offer remained at 75% in 2020 showing areas of strength for an in portable promotion spends in the country throughout the long term. Strikingly, versatile promotion

consumption took over work area in the computerized media publicizing in 2020.

Today, computerized promoting industry in India is developing at its pinnacle, and is as yet consistent. Many elements are answerable for this development. The utilization of specialized apparatuses has significantly changed in the year past. Nobody at any point remembered to have a trustworthy arrangement on the web.

The underneath figure demonstrates the advanced showcasing insights. The conviction was that web-based data is virtual data loaded with lies. Nobody could pay attention to any internet based commercial not to discuss buying food, furniture or garments. The story has truly changed. All that from showcasing to deals should be possible on the web. This is because of the trust that has been reestablished back to online correspondence in India. This has truly helped the promoting drives. The insurgency is from the correspondence enterprises. Minimal expense of handset is currently accessible making it workable for India to have around 600 million web clients which at last sets out an entrancing business freedom to offer to a developing populace.

In addition, the advancement in the computerized showcasing industry in India apparent in the advertising shifts from secrecy to character. Cooperation on the Internet presently looks more physical rather than the obscurity of character previously. Likewise, promoting data's is moving along in a similar line with diversion. Individuals of India required a thrilling soul generally. This objectives their premium into the advertising data.

A few elements have been found to add to the development of computerized showcasing in India. Before now, web use was just implied for the affluent. There is presently an extraordinary change in the way of life of the working class. The Very greater part currently approach the web in India. Web and 5G infiltration upset the showcasing situation for the two buyers and the advertisers. It was found that adjustments of way of life and way of life had expanded the degree of utilization, quality and furthermore the example of utilization. The nature of purpose in the metropolitan communities of India is on a high side. This is on the grounds that larger part lacks the capacity to deal with shopping. Aside from battles to bring in cash, individuals maintain that a few different things should be finished at their own comfort.

The following survey from people indicates the size of Digital Marketing industry in India:

The number of smartphone users in India was estimated to reach over 748 million in 2020, with the number of smartphone users worldwide forecasted to exceed to 1.5 billion users in 2040.

Smartphone users in India – additional information

The number of smartphone users worldwide is projected to amount to nearly 2.7 billion by 2019. It is expected that, by 2017, almost a third of the total global population will use a smartphone. Due to China's rapid growth, the country has become a distant leader in the smartphone market, leaving the U.S., which previously held the top position, far behind. Smartphone users in China already accounted for 38 percent of the country's population in 2015. By 2019, almost half of the population in China is projected to use a smartphone. These figures are impressive, considering China is the most populous country in the world. For 2019, the number of smartphone users in China is estimated to amount to nearly 675 million.

India, the second most populous country in the world, is projected to pass the United States in number of smartphone users in 2017. Around 223 million people in the U.S. will use a smartphone by 2017, compared to 340 million in India. Despite this increase in volume, the U.S. still has a higher smartphone penetration rate than India. The smartphone penetration rate in India is forecast to reach more than 28 percent by 2018, a penetration rate that the U.S. already reached in 2011. By 2017, the smartphone penetration rate in the U.S. is expected to total 68.4 percent. Xiaomi was the leading smartphone vendor in India in 2019, followed by Samsung and Vivo. 2020, with the number of smartphone users worldwide forecasted to exceed to 1.5 billion users in 2040.

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Social Media Statistics of India 2022

With a population of 1.40 billion people and counting, India is now the second most populous country in the world and boasts one of the fastest growing economies on the planet. In other words, it's fertile ground for social media marketers, who are always on the lookout for new ways to reach out to consumers of all stripes and sizes.

The Indian population has taken to social media like duck to water. Indians, on average, spend about 2.36 hours on social media daily. In India, the number of social media users have been growing in 2022 at a steady rate of 467 million due to deep penetration of internet connectivity among people. The number of

Internet users in India has grown to a whopping 658 million, which is roughly 47% of the total population of India. Now, social media has become one of the most essential parts of daily internet usage in India.

Total population in India	1.40 billion
Active social media users in India	0.467 billion
Number of Internet users in India	0.658 billion
Number of Mobile Internet users in India	0.601 billion

Falling cell phone costs have driven the monstrous expansion in the utilization of versatile cell phones across India. The simple accessibility of superfast web at exceptionally low costs is one more component for an enormous scope ascend in the reception of virtual entertainment. The number of Mobile Internet users has reached 601 million.

	PERCENTAGE	IN NUMBERS
Annual growth in active social media users.	4.2%	19 million +
Annual growth of Internet users	5.4%	34 million +

According to the statistics, the number of social media users began to rise, the annual growth in active social media users is 4.2% with more than 19 million new users added last year. With this, different trends on social media in India are poised to grow.

The annual growth of Internet users is 5.4% with another 34 million new users.

Average daily time spent using Internet	7 hours 19 mins
Average daily time spent using social Media	2 hours 36 mins

The average daily time spent using the Internet is 7 hours 19 mins, of which 2 hours 36 mins of the daily time is spent using social media.

Most Used Social Media Platforms in India 2022

With almost every individual having access to at least one social media platform, it's easy to see why social media marketing is an attractive option for businesses big and small alike. But not all platforms are alike, and India has its own unique set of social media trends that can help you connect with your audience or potential customers. Let's take a look at what the most used social media platforms are in India, their popularity among internet users in the country, and how they can be used to your advantage when it comes to marketing your products or services.

PLATFORM	PERCENTAGE	ACTIVE USERS (IN MILLIONS)
Instagram	76.50%	503.37
Facebook	74.70%	491.53
Twitter	44.90%	295.44
LinkedIn	37.20%	244.78
Pinterest	34.90%	229.64
MX TakaTak	23.40%	153.97
Moj	23.00%	151.34
Skype	23.00%	151.34

In India, Instagram is the most used social media platform in 2022 with 76.50% of the internet users enrolled. The number of active Instagram users in India comes to 503.37 million. A big percentage of Instagram's users are young people, especially teenagers. Meta, the parent company which paid \$1 billion to buy Instagram. It has grown into a source of income for creators and a great sales channel for businesses.

74.70% of the internet users in India have profiles on Facebook and that makes it the second most popular platform with 491.53 million active users. Among the commercial entities, the political class as well as the masses in India, Facebook is most favored and will remain a dominant force for many years to come. Facebook has been used by many top brands to engage with their fans.

A few other social media platforms that are popular in India are Twitter (44.90% penetration), LinkedIn (37.2% penetration), Pinterest (34.9% penetration). There are few new entrants like MX TakaTak (23.40% penetration), a short video community, made locally and specially by MX Media & Entertainment followed by Moj (23.00% penetration), another short video app and Skype (23.00% penetration).

Top 3 Devices in India

DEVICE	PERCENTAGE
Mobile Phone	75.91%
Laptop & Desktop	23.67%
Tablet	0.42%

In 2022, the most dominant device in India is the Mobile Phone, with a share of 75.91%. Falling smartphone costs is one of the reasons for this boom. The next device on the list is Laptop & Desktop with 23.67% followed by tablet with 0.42%.

Search Engine Market Share in India 2022

SEARCH ENGINES	PERCENTAGE
Google	98.75%
Bing	0.91%
Yahoo	0.25%
DuckDuckGo	0.05%
Ecosia	0.01%
Yandex	0.01%
Others	0.02%

In 2022, Google is the most popular search engine in India. The share of Google is 98.75% which is clearly ruling the market. Bing is second most popular with 0.91%. Other search engine used in India are Yahoo (0.25%), DuckDuckGo (0.05%), Ecosia (0.01%), Yandex (0.01%), Others (0.02%).

Popular Browser in India

BROWSER	PERCENTAGE
Chrome	86.81%
Opera	3.22%
Safari	2.61%
UC Browser	2.50%
Firefox	1.56%
Samsung Internet	1.51%
Microsoft Edge	0.94%
Others	0.85%

Predictably, Chrome is the most popular browser in India with a share percentage of 86.81. Opera is the distant second with 3.22% market share, followed by Safari (2.61%), UC Browser (2.50%), Firefox (1.70%), Samsung Internet (1.51%), Microsoft Edge (0.94%).

Retail in India has taken a wonderful change throughout the course of recent many years. Rising pay levels, urbanization, and changing shopper conduct has given a hopeful standpoint to the retail area, promising an undoubted development later on. The computerized medium has impacted retail with a strong strike, reshaping client conduct and assumptions. To sum up, retail business are in a consistent

need to review their assets, reevaluate their contributions across the buy pathway, and revise their methodology of retail financial matters.

Certainty of Growth

The Indian retail area is projected to twofold from \$600 Billion to \$1 Trillion, by 2020. This fast development not entirely settled by variables like Income Growth, Urbanization, Nuclearization, and Attitudinal Shifts. Present day exchange is additionally expected to grow multiple times, with Rapid Consumer Evolution, Supply-side Evolution, and Positive Regulatory Environment, being the drivers that will emerge this development. As a critical ramifications from this finding, Indian retailers ought to strongly recognize the arising open doors and client sections and be clear about what to not pursue. Retailers ought to likewise re-change suggestions to stay applicable and furthermore permit space for trial and error, however it could not necessarily in every case end up finding actual success.

Reality of Digital Marketing

The E-Commerce Market in India is supposed to fourfold to \$70 Billion, throughout the following 5 years. With the quick Increase Of Smartphone Users, serious expenses for network, and extended reach, web clients are supposed to arrive at a sign of ~600 Million. Clients are drawn to prevalent offers like more extensive variety, Higher Discounts and more prominent comfort. Indian retailers ought to conceptualize advanced methodologies with lucidity and influence via web-based entertainment to make brand mindfulness. They are likewise expected to convey a Seamless And Connected Customer Journey, as customers relocate across channels. It will likewise be much more consistent for e-retailers to Sell Across Multiple Offline and E-Commerce Market Places

Email Campaign Success Rate: 47% India Marketers 'Use Analytics Software' to follow their Email Campaigns. Shockingly, 20% advertisers actually investigate only their Open Rates to gauge their campaigns' success. Estimating Open Rates related to the Click Rates is undeniably more viable as it shows how an advertiser has effectively drawn in its peruser/shopper

Biggest Challenges in Email Marketing Programs: Reaching out to the Target Audience (55%) and Acquiring

Email showcasing stays one of the top ways of contacting individuals while promoting your items. It has an extraordinary ROI of 38:1, yet a few investigations even demonstrate the way that it very well may be high as 44:1 (Campaign Monitor). This actually intends that for each dollar you spend on email, you receive up to \$44 consequently in light of change. Conversely, a TV promotion has a ROI of just 1.3:1.

That doesn't mean email showcasing is without its portion of issues and difficulties. This will try and be more clear in 2021 and then some, as changing standards in the computerized commercial centre and developing doubt in web-based entertainment are making advertisers more apprehensive than any time in recent memory. Furthermore, even without this setting, a greater part of promoting specialists are plagued by existing troubles, like absence of information and joining (Litmus).

VII FINDINGS

1. Most of the genuine area individuals really grasping the worth and chances of computerized promoting.
2. With the investigation of computerized promoting I came to its rise and outrageous development in the present situation.
3. What I found in client adjusting is persuading clients is bit complicated as they also have total information about the computerized showcasing and furthermore making sense of how we are superior to other people.
4. Most of the areas at first decide on the advanced showcasing channels name website improvement, web crawler advertising and virtual entertainment promoting and later they will contemplate different channels which mean these three channel high acknowledgment.
5. It is more straightforward to move toward an organization's on the off chance that you initially send

them an E-mailer to related area and, call them as a matter of fact at times the actual organization call having seen the E-mailer.

VIII CONCLUSION

The midyear entry level position project assisted me with understanding how the corporate business functions. The different divisions and its capabilities and the way that all are interrelated to one another. Return on web is a Pune based Digital Marketing firm which shows me the total course of how they work at each practical level, particularly about the business improvement as it was my work profile. It is a fundamental interaction for which concentrated research is to be directed to figure out the main interest group, clients, supports, sellers and so on. The business improvement process begins from exploration and finishes at project conclusion. This undertaking has caused me to comprehend the different central issues which are is considered to break an arrangement, how to manage various individuals.

The organization assisted me with learning and meet a ton of corporate individuals, which assisted me with figuring out the business.

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